

Supplementary Figure 1. Illustrations of offline replay of online behavioral experiences. **(A)** Hippocampal replay as a sequential activation of hippocampal place cells during sharp wave ripples (SWRs). **(B)** Cortical replay: High-dimensional behavior or stimulus sequences can be represented as an abstract sequence encoded by cortical population activity; cortical replay can be identified by the decoded sequence from spike activity of cortical neurons during the offline state. Sequential reactivation of a spatiotemporal event is common in both hippocampal and cortical replay, and there is a coherent correspondence in neural (or abstract) sequences between the online and offline states.

Supplementary Figure 2. Search results (1992-2022) based on the keywords “memory replay” OR “memory reactivation” in Google Scholar publications.